

Review report on extended abstract titled “APICURON, A Platform for Crediting & Recognizing Research Assets”

Authors (alphabetically by last name)

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Feedback Reviewer 1 Serafeim Chatzopoulos

Reviewer 1					
ID	Relevance	Significance	Novelty & Originality	Clarity & Quality of Presentation	Overall Judgement
ID10	5	4	4	5	Accept

Your work on the APICURON platform presents a very interesting and relevant contribution to expanding recognition within Open Science, particularly for non-traditional research resources (or assets). The platform’s focus on crediting diverse contributions such as curated data, software, and workflows directly addresses a critical gap in current evaluation and has the potential to significantly influence research practices. Moreover, the integration with research repositories, and especially with ORCID profiles, adds a practical dimension that could enhance researcher visibility and credit for their work.

Feedback Reviewer 2 Laura Himanen

Reviewer 2					
ID	Relevance	Significance	Novelty & Originality	Clarity & Quality of Presentation	Overall Judgement
ID10	4	4	3	3	Accept

This abstract describes a service that enables the recognition of non-traditional scientific contributions, especially efforts in collecting, curating and processing data. While this is an important issue in moving towards research evaluation that takes diverse scientific activities more comprehensively into consideration, the abstract fails to explain how this specific service achieves its aim to provide comprehensive credit and recognition. As it is now, it seems more like promotional advertising material. Therefore in the final poster I would like to see a more detailed and technical description of how the service works and aims to fulfil its mission.

